

Protocol S1: Design and cloning of tyrosinase gRNAs into T7/ccdB plasmid

Timing: 1 week

Here we provide a protocol for the design and cloning of gRNAs into a vector that can then be used as template for *in vitro* transcription of the gRNA (Figure S1). Specifically, we show here the generation of a gRNA targeting tyrosinase (*Tyr*). Using gRNA's targeting *Tyr* gives a quick and easy read out of an injectionist's success rate as pups from successfully injected C57Bl6NTac embryos will show patches of white or complete white coat colour (Figure S2).

Other methods for gRNA synthesis including PCR based methods or commercially purchased synthetic gRNAs are available. Our protocol provides an efficient and robust way for gRNA generation. As the gRNA oligos are first cloned into a vector and then sequence verified, the gRNA is transcribed from a sequence verified template. PCR based methods can introduce single bp changes that can potentially lead to off target cutting due to changed gRNA sequence. Part of the cloning protocol described here has been modified from the Zhang lab original protocol available on Addgene. (https://media.addgene.org/cms/filer_public/e6/5a/e65a9ef8-c8ac-4f88-98da-3b7d7960394c/zhang-lab-general-cloning-protocol.pdf).

The gRNA cloning vector (T7-gRNA_ccdB) contains a T7 promoter with ccdB, flanked by BsaI sites, followed by the sgRNA backbone. Upon digestion of the vector with BsaI, a pair of annealed gRNA oligos can be cloned scarlessly into the vector in front of the sgRNA backbone (Figure S1).

Materials:

T7-gRNA_ccdB vector (Figure S1)
BsaI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, FD0294)
Fast Alkaline Phosphatase (Thermo Fisher Scientific, EF0654)
QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, 28104)
T4 DNA Ligase Reaction Buffer (NEB, B0202)
T4 Polynucleotide Kinase (NEB, M0201)
Quick Ligation Kit (NEB, M2200)
One Shot TOP10 Chemically Competent E. coli (Invitrogen, C4040)
LB-kan plates
QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit (Qiagen, 27104)
DraI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, FD0224)
MEGAscript T7 transcription kit (Ambion AM1354)

Procedure:

Identify CRISPR/Cas9 target sites using <http://bioinfo.gp.cnb.csic.es/tools/breakingcas/> [29] or a similar tool that searches for efficient gRNA sites. In addition, where possible, pick gRNAs that follow the guidelines from Doench *et al.*, (2014) [30] avoiding C and T upstream of the PAM, G downstream of the PAM and T within the PAM. As a control for microinjections the following Tyrosinase gRNA works well (Figure S2).

GCTCCCATCTTCAGCAGATGTGG

Order FW oligo with: 5' – ATAGG GCTCCCATCTTCAGCAGATG - 3'

Order RV oligo with: 3' - CGAGGGTAGAAGTCGTCTAC CAAA - 5'

1) Digest 5µg of T7-gRNA_ccdB vector with BsaI for 1h at 37C:

5µg T7-gRNA_ccdB
1µL BsaI
1µL FastAP
2µL 10x FastDigestion Buffer
X ul H2O to a total of 20ul

Figure S2. Mice obtained following cytoplasmic injection of Cas9 mRNA with *Tyr* gRNA. Successful injection of the RNA mixture will result in F0 mice with an albino coat colour ranging from a few hairs to a complete albino mouse. This enables a quick read out of an injectionists success and will provide a useful benchmarking.